

CORPORATE SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITIES OF LEATHER BASED INDUSTRIES (A STUDY ON IMPLEMENTATION OF ‘MOST’ ANALYSIS)

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ABSTRACT

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is the sum of the voluntary actions taken by a company to address the economic, social and environmental impacts of its business operations and the concerns of its principal stakeholders. The European Commission (2011) published a new definition of CSR: “The responsibility of enterprises for their impacts on society.” Every CSR strategy requires the development and implementation of an employee communication program to convey the corporate direction, objectives, innovation and performance of its CSR efforts. These requirements are to be fulfilled through MOST Analysis. This research paper aims to analyse the concept of corporate responsibilities of leather-based industries using M.O.S.T. (Mission, Objectives, Strategy and Tactics) Analysis. This analysis attempts to answer the Mission, Objectives, Strategy and Tactics of CSR performed Leather-based industries. Critically evaluate the concept of corporate social responsibility, discuss how the M.O.S.T. Analysis helps to perform. We conclude that M.O.S.T. Analysis helps to the social responsibility of Leather Based Industries to the extent that circumstances permit, positively or negatively.

1. INTRODUCTION

The government of India has made it mandatory for the firms to be responsible for the development of society and contribute to environmental sustainability by enacting ‘The Companies Act, 2013. Before this legislation, it was all up to the desire of the firms if they want to contribute to the development of the society or not and even they wanted to contribute to this practice of welfare they could spend any amount according to their will. But with the enforcement of this act, all the companies making a specific amount of profit were brought under

this ambit and the amount to be spent was also fixed and also the reporting of CSR activities was made mandatory leading to better accountancy of activities. Hence, it can be said that the majority of companies have accepted the fact that it owes its responsibility to the country, the society and the environment from the resources of which it is taking advantage and is prospering. Also over the years, it has been seen that CSR initiatives and the amount spent on them has increased and every year some new areas to be focused on are added to their core development areas.

M.O.S.T. analysis is a highly-structured method for providing targets to team members at every level of an organisation. Working from the top down ensures that you retain focus on the goal which matters most to your organisation. It is an extremely powerful tool, often used to give businesses and other organisations a fresh sense of purpose and capability. M.O.S.T. analysis is how you start to tie lofty ambitions and idealistic visions to top achievable goals and a successful business. As a system, it breaks down the communication barriers between different levels on the same team by asking at every stage “How does this help us reach our next level of targets?” In this way, every tactic employed has to be justified in terms of reaching strategies, which in turn must contribute to objectives, which must, finally, contribute to your mission. This analysis helps the company to reach its objectives of helping customers in the shop as soon as a problem arises, which contributes to the mission, selling more products. It can be applied to many areas of a business, from its most obvious applications in sales, marketing and business growth to internal processes and human resources.

A Corporate Social Responsibility Plan, or CSR Strategy, is a company’s way to give back to society beyond the for-profit strategies that determine your viability as a business. The concept of corporate responsibility helps extend the reach of a business and gives them a strategic way to impact the world in meaningful ways. There are four types of corporate social responsibility: direct philanthropic giving, environmental sustainability, ethical business practices, and economic responsibility. Some business integrates a combination of all four in their CSR Plan. CSR can positively impact employee attitudes and expectations by giving them a different perspective of their community and providing a new skill set. Participation in volunteer

work or environmental initiatives helps staff to grow personally, from new awareness of social issues to self-awareness of their environmental impact. CSR is not a one-off initiative. It needs to be fostered and embraced throughout the company. At positive Adventures, we believe strongly that businesses of all sizes should demonstrate social accountability, and we work with others to help implement programs that are effective and lasting.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF M.O.S.T. (MISSION, OBJECTIVES, STRATEGY AND TACTICS) ANALYSIS

2.1 MISSION

A good mission is ambitious and essential to broader business success. It could even be the entire reason for the organisations' existence. Once it has been established, the rest of the M.O.S.T. analysis can begin. The mission should be reviewed when they have succeeded or are found to be flawed. In accordance with laws, regulations and code of ethics as well as manners and customs, to improve and expand the manufacturing business raising the required standard, and contributing to the economy with environmental consciousness. An accurate relationship between respect for the rules, honesty, success and to abide by services and leather quality consistent with environmental sustainability. A preliminary step to create proposals and leather collections of articles.

2.2 OBJECTIVES

A good objective sets a clear target to achieve within a tight time-frame. Objectives should be Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Realistic and Timely (S.M.A.R.T.), otherwise goal-creep will set in and objectives will become fuzzy and difficult to implement. Ideally, it will complement your other objectives to compound successes across the M.O.S.T. analysis. Objectives should be reviewed if they are found not to help the mission. The core objectives of CSR are the initiative of Leather Industries.

2.3 STRATEGIES

A good strategy is the options open to achieve objectives. These may be quite complex, involving many tactics, and they may overlap to an extent. Strategies are an implementation detail. Strategies offer a way to quickly review and group the tactics implemented on the ground floor, so they make sense as methods to achieve your objectives. If strategies do not accurately describe the tactics being used or do not work directly towards your objectives, you should review them.

2.4 TACTICS

A good tactic is small and S.M.A.R.T. with effective tactics, your strategies will quickly lead to completed objectives. Tactics are the methods you will use to carry out your strategies. They should be simple and relatively discrete processes that can easily be understood and carried out even by people who don't have a high-level overview of the M.O.S.T. analysis. If your tactics are inefficient and complex in practice, or there are unexpected obstacles to implementing them successfully, they should be reviewed.

“Strategy without tactics is the slowest route to victory.

Tactics without strategy are the noise before defeat.”

- Sun Tzu.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

To design the present study scientifically, the researcher surveyed a good amount of research work and literature carried out in the area of corporate social responsibility. There are some of the reviews of the studies which had been previously undertaken in the field of CSR.

Saiful Islam and ParagJafarSiddique (2014) analyzed the performance of the leather industry in Bangladesh and made its comparison with India, Pakistan and China. They analyzed the export of the leather industry from the year 2004-2013. This study has revealed that Bangladesh had the potentiality to invest more and expand in the leather industry which substantially because of raw hides and skin exports.

A.Sahasranaman (2014), in his article, “Some thoughts about India’s Leather sector Exports” opined that the Indian Leather Industry has been able to get its legitimate share of the world market for leather and leather products. When one compares the condition of the industry in the early 1980s with its current situation, there were many facets of the Industry that were truly impressive.

Mwinyikione, Mwinyihija (2014), their discussion in their paper titled, “Emerging World Leather Trends and Continental Shift on Leather and Leather goods Production”, had yielded several fundamental issues of importance to the leather sector. It’s had regained its prestigious position and provided credence to the sector’s future expectation.

OmwenoNyameyioEnock& Dr. KundanBasavaraji, Kuvempu University (2013) CSR has been assuming greater importance in the corporate world in the 21st century. Indian Government has drafted guidelines for CSR practices, which of late proposed companies to contribute a percentage share towards that cause (CSR). This study compares the CSR activities of Tata Company and ITC Company in different areas i.e. environmental friendliness, social accountability, employee safety, human rights promotion and healthcare etc. The study also focuses on the reporting methods used by these companies. From this study, it is observed that all the two big private companies of the country are directly engaged in social responsibility in various areas, from innovation in agriculture & education to saving the environment. It is concluded that environment, education, community involvement and health care activities practiced as CSR by both companies.

Bhupender&Vikas Kumar Joshiya (2012) told that CSR expanded to include both economic and social interests. Companies have become more transparent in accounting and display „public reporting“ due to pressures from various stakeholders. In this research paper CSR status, challenges of CSR, policies for CSR in India are studied. The concept of CSR is now firmly rooted in the global business agenda. But to move from theory to concrete action, many obstacles need to be overcome. Many positive outcomes can arise when businesses adopt a policy of social responsibility.

4. NEED OF THE STUDY

Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) is an effective way of achieving and maintaining sound business management. By carrying out social responsibility a company can enhance its economic value and brand image as well as benefit to society. Besides, companies and other organisations are required to have accountability towards stakeholders such as consumers, investors, employees, residents etc. while utilising the resources of society.

Many companies are putting more emphasis on Corporate Social Responsibility's Triple Bottom Line: People, Planet and Profit. These economic, social and ecological values help to measure an organisation's success and impact on its stakeholders. CSR is a vehicle through which companies give something back to society, but the challenge before the companies is to identify CSR priorities and the areas of the invention which are meaningful in the context of social development. So, there is a need to study and understand the CSR practices being taken by different corporate houses.

Besides the responsibility towards society, the companies are responsible to work in a manner so that they earn profit and increase their profitability. Companies have a responsibility towards shareholders, investors, creditors. So, there is a need to study what is the impact of CSR practices on the profitability of the business. To make an overall study that to what extent the companies in India are doing CSR practices, there is a need to study CSR practices in Leather industries in Vellore District.

5. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Corporate Social Responsiveness is one such factor that emphasizes actions and activities known to the individuals of the organization in caring out CSR activities. This aspect is interlinked with the organizations Corporate Ethics, which is a form of applied ethics or professional ethics that examines ethical principles and moral or ethical problems that arise in a business environment. It applies to all aspects of business conduct and is relevant to the conduct of individuals and business organizations as a whole especially when catering to the activities of

CSR. It is an ethical framework that suggests that an entity, be it an organization or individual, must act for the benefit of the individual and the society at large. It is a concept whereby companies carry out CSR activities with their employees in involving them in initiatives that benefit to society. Whereas, MOST Analysis is a simple framework tool for analysing or planning the detail of what an organisation does. It helps to frame questions, starting from the high-level mission of the organisation and digging right down to the detail of individual tactics. The mission of an organisation should be determined by the organisation what do you do. Objectives start with the translation of the mission into the overall intent that drives the strategy process. The strategy includes the high-level decisions that shape what is done and how. Tactical planning takes strategic decisions and figures out how to implement them in practice. Through MOST analysis, the CSR may strengthen and create more profitability in the organisation. In this direction, the researcher attempted to analyse how the MOST Analysis will help to improve CSR practices and profitability.

6. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The present study was undertaken with the following objectives in mind.

1. To examine the social responsibility of the employee exist in Leather industries in Vellore District.
2. To study and analyse the effectiveness of the CSR activities through MOST Analysis as perceived by the employees
3. To suggest suitable measures for improving CSR activities through MOST Analysis.

7. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

- The MOST Analysis tool comes in handy. This tool is meant to work from the top-down, with each successful point becoming a little more specific as it goes. Let's take a quick look at each of the four elements of the MOST Analysis tool to better understand how they can drive your organization forward.

- The mission is the statement created by top-level management. The overall reason is to plan what the company wants to accomplish. The more specific that you can be when defining your mission, the more success you will have later on trying to define the remaining points within the tool.
- Objectives are one step down from your mission. Think of these as a collection of individual goals that will add up to reaching your overall mission. Just like with the mission, objectives should be specific enough to guide your decision making and planning for the future. With your mission in place, it should be relatively easy to develop a list of a few objectives.
- Strategy means the actions that should be taken to accomplish the organisational objectives. So the leather companies are to prepare a suitable strategy to achieve the goal on a long-term basis.
- The final point in the MOST tools is the tactics that the company uses to enact the strategies. The tactics should be the specific details that will guide your daily activities. Using the tactics to dictate the employees' daily activities is the best way to make sure what are doing today and it will guide them in the right direction toward the overall mission.
- The idea behind MOST is that it will help to organize the activities in support of each other so they are all heading in the same direction. Without this kind of cohesion between your activities, the future can suddenly look bleak.
- However, once the business is up and running, it is easy to lose track of that plan or purpose for the business.
- There is so much to do daily that it is easy to forget about the plan and get lost in the details of the daily routine. When the daily activities that take up most of the time are no longer aligned with the vision that the company has for the future of the business and the company has a hard time reaching the goals. Staying on track requires a close connection between long-term goals and short-term activities.

8. CONCLUSION

This research paper is on the discussion of Mission, Objectives, Strategies and Tactics of CSR Initiative Leather Based Industries. This study concludes the actual result of Mission, Objectives, Strategies and Tactics of CSR Initiative Leather Based Industries with the help of (M.O.S.T) Analysis tool. This tool implies the simple framework tool for analysing or planning the detail of starting from the high-level mission of the organisation and digging right down to the detail of tactics. At the end of the analysis, it shows the Detailed Mission of CSR Initiative Leather-based industries identifies. An accurate relationship between respect for the rules, honesty, success and to abide by services and leather quality consistent with environmental sustainability. In accordance with laws, regulations and code of ethics as well as manners and customs. To promote CSR for creating shared value, integrating corporate processes, social & environment processes and creating a win-win relationship everything respects that surrounds it: human, animals and environment, these principles inscribed in the company's DNA.

In the aspect of Objectives, it prescribes the framework of Economic performance, Stakeholder engagement, Eco-efficiency and a Great place to work. In these measure helps to promote the Organisation fulfilments along with corporate responsibilities. And, Strategic planning of Corporate Social Responsibility is a sensible step for any company, regardless of its business, size or geographical area it has become Instrumental for companies to meet the Social, Ethical and Environmental expectations of the Civil Society. It is reflected through strategies adopted by companies to improve its Social, Ethical and Environmental impact. The CSR Strategic positioning possible, spanning within the benefits. Such as a reduction of risk exposure and opportunities for financial returns. A good strategy with effective tactics will quickly lead to completed objectives, as a way to reach the Mission. "Strategy without tactics is the slowest route to victory, tactics without strategy is the noise before defeat" – Sun Tzu. Finally, the Research Topic identifies the positive as well as negative suggestions with the help of M.O.S.T. Analysis. Such as its compliance with Standards, Environmental-Friendly, avoiding expenditure, reducing the risk of exposure, Sustainable Innovation of CSR dictate the Social, Ethical and Environmental standards in the Future.

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